
DETERMINATION OF RADIOACTIVITY CONCENTRATION AND POSSIBLE ENVIRONMENTAL HAZARDS OF THE TAR SAND DEPOSITS OF ONDO STATE, SOUTH WESTERN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT.

Gamma ray spectrometric analyses were carried out on 25 samples of bituminous sand collected from five different locations (Ilubirin, Agbabu, Mile 2, Igbokoda and Okitipupa) of Okitipupa area in Ondo State. The samples were air dried, weighed and sealed for 28 days to allow them attain a state of secular equilibrium. They were thereafter analyzed for gamma emitting radio nuclides using the gamma-ray spectrometer fitted with a calibrated Canberra cervical co-axial high purity germanium detector (HPGe) system at the Radiation and Health Physics Laboratory in the Department of Physics, University of Ibadan. The objectives were to determine the presence and level of radioactivity concentrations of selected radionuclides, to assess the impact of the radioactivity on the environment. The range of average radioactive concentration obtained was 12.04 ± 0.48 in Okitipupa to 20.13 ± 0.24 in Agbadu, 0.968 ± 0.07 in Ilubirin to 6.79 ± 0.05 in Agbadu and 18.82 ± 0.26 in Ilubirin to 105.76 ± 0.78 in Agbadu all in Bq/Kg for of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K respectively. The mean dose equivalent obtained was $20.10 \mu\text{Sv}$ which was below the world average of $70 \mu\text{Sv}$. The study confirmed the presence of radionuclides in the bituminous sands but their activity levels are low and thus are not expected to constitute any health hazard on the environment.

KEYWORDS: bituminous sand, radioactivity, health hazard, Okitipupa.

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INTRODUCTION

Awareness of exposures to natural radioactivity in both the industrial and environmental domain is growing. Unfortunately, common errors in associating ambient radioactivity with the nuclear industry and indeed the assumption that radioactivity is in some way unnatural frequently arises. Virtually all materials and environments in our planet are both radioactive and exposed naturally to ionizing radiation. Studies on the radioactivity of rocks and mineral have found applications in many fields of solid earth physics and applied geophysics. The rate of radioactive decay of certain naturally occurring elements in rocks provide a power tool of dating geologic events. The heat produced by radioactive disintegration is an important source of thermal energy that brings about metamorphism and igneous activity of significant importance is the use of radioactivity survey in geological mapping since different rock type can be recognized from their distinctive radioactive signatures. Applications to environmental problems such as detection of radioactive pollution in soils, ground water and air are also of significant importance.

Bituminous sands are composed of sand, heavy oil, mineral rich clay, and water in various proportions. In its raw state, bitumen is a semi-solid, viscous and sticky black substance that requires chemical alterations to make it liquid enough to transport by pipeline. Parnell et al, (1990), suggested that bitumen can also be formed from radioactive bombardment of the molecules of migrating hydrocarbon. Irrespective of the mode of formation, bitumen in sedimentary rocks attests of the former presence of fluid hydrocarbon in the environment (Rasmussen, 1997). Analysis of samples of tar impregnated sands from selected boreholes using the X-ray diffractometer, model FW 1011 generator and PW 1050 goniometer (Adegoke et al 1980), revealed the existence of four groups

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of clay minerals from the diffraction patterns. These are: (i) Kaolinite (ii) Mica, (iii) Mixed layer minerals and (iv) Chlorite and Smectite. A few samples contain pyroxenes and/or clinozoisile. When the mineral distribution results are considered along with the lithology of the sampled core materials, there was an indication of two groups of sediments.

- (a) quartz-rich sands with little clay containing abundant kaolinite.
- (b) predominantly clay and silty clay containing dark minerals as indicated by the presence of pyroxene and high iron content (dark grey colour turn brownish-red on heating), mica and large amount of smectite.

Geologically, uranium, thorium, radium and radon are markedly oxyphile in nature, occurring mainly as oxides, silicates, phosphates, vanadales, arsenates, selenites and telluride in highly fractionated magmas and hydrothermal solutions and are thus found in acid igneous rocks (e.g granites), pegmatites and hydrothermal deposits. These radioactive elements, however have biophile tendencies and are found in various organisms. They also tend to be concentrated under certain conditions in organic compound, such as humus, coal petroleum, bitumen and thucholites (Boyle, 1982).

Radon, the only gaseous daughter of uranium decay, which is also a noble gas, can migrate much more easily than any of the other daughter elements. Exposure to natural airborne radon (Rn) has been identified as the primary mode of radiation exposure for many population living in areas underlain by crystalline bedrock (particularly felsic acid igneous rocks), or by radioelement-rich sedimentary rocks (Banks et al., 1995). Indoor radon concentration study in home has now moved from obscurity to one of the most feared environment hazards. United States Environmental Protection Agency estimates that 15,000 to 20,000 deaths result from radon induced lung cancer each year in the United States (Gates and Gunderson, 1992). Also Statens, (1994) showed that radon was responsible for 150-130 lung cancer cases (10-20% of the total) annually recorded in Norway. The finding of health physicists on indoor radon are however constrained by the geologic environment because the processes responsible for the generation and transmission in indoor radon are directly controlled by geology whilst, its concentration, the third process, is less so (Gates and Gunderson 1992).

Gamma-Ray spectrometric method, though relatively unimportant in comparison with other geophysical techniques, is becoming increasingly useful in mineral/ oil exploration. Gamma-ray spectrometry has the ability to measure gamma emitters directly in the original sample without the need for chemical separation. Also, quantitative determination of radionuclide in the sample can be carried out with this technique. The relatively known high concentration of radioactive elements in petroleum and bitumen compared to other rocks emphasizes the need to determine their contents in the bituminous sands of Ondo State. Therefore, for a complete geochemical characterization of the bituminous sands, the source and abundance of radioisotopes (K, Th, U) need to be determined and the importance evaluated as an exploration method in mapping the occurrence and extent of the mineral/oil as well as their impact of the environment.

GEOLOGY OF THE SITE

The area covered in this study lies between Longitudes $4^{\circ}48'$ and $4^{\circ}54'$ East and Latitudes $6^{\circ}35'$ and $6^{\circ}39'$ North. The area falls within the 1:50,000 federal surveys topographic sheet 282 (Okitipupa S.E). Ilubirin lies in the central portion of the area. It is bounded to the north by a village called Foriku and to the south by a town called Agbabu. Although the area lies with the tropical rain forest belt of South- Western Nigeria, accessibility is generally good, consisting of tarred roads, seasoned lateritic roads and footpaths. However, there are large tracts of lands, which are not accessible due to either thick forest cover or marshy terrain.

The tar sand belt and the associated bitumen occur within the Nigerian sector of the Dahomey basin. Klemme, (1995) showed that it is a coastal sedimentary basin formed from the marginal (Type 5) pull- apart basin. The basin extends from Ghana-Ivory Coast boundary across Togo and Republic of Benin to Western Nigeria (figure 1)

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Fig. 1 : regional geological map of dahomey basin (after Adegoke et al. , 1980)

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

Method of measurement.

A total of 25 samples were collected from five different locations (Iubirin, Agbabu, Mile 2, Igbokoda and Okitipupa) of Okitipupa area in Ondo state. The air dried samples were weighed and sealed for 28 days to allow them attain a state of secular equilibrium. The detector used for the radioactivity measurements was a lead-shielded 76mmX76mm NaI (TI) detector crystal (802 series, Canberra Inc) coupled to a Canberra series 10 plus multichannel analyser (MCA) (model no. 1104) through a preamplifier. It has a resolution (FWHM) of about 8% at an energy of 0.662mev (¹³⁷Cs) which is considered adequate to distinguish the gamma ray energies of interest in the present study.

The samples were placed symmetrically on top of the detector and measured for a period of 10Hrs (36 000 secs).

CALCULATION OF RADIOACTIVITY CONCENTRATION.

The activity concentrations in the samples were evaluated using the relation below;

$$A_c = \frac{A}{\epsilon P m}$$

Where A_c =Activity concentration in Bq/kg, A =net peak area, T =counting time(secs)
 ϵ =efficiency, P =probability of gamma emission, m =mass of sample in kg

CALCULATION OF RADIUM EQUIVALENT

The radium equivalents in **Bq/Kg** were calculated using the relation below;

$$C_U + 1.43C_{Th} + 0.0077C_K$$

Where C_U =activity concentration of uranium, C_{Th} =activity concentration of thorium
 C_K =activity concentration of potassium

CALCULATION OF ABSORBED DOSE.

Radiation emitted by a radioactive substance is absorbed by any material it encounters, dead material or living cell. Every kilogram (kg) of material absorbs some energy (joule),the J/kg is used for the measurement of absorbed dose. In radiation protection, that unit is called gray (Gy). The corresponding absorbed dose rates have been calculated using the relationship derived by Beck et al., (1972) which is given as;

$$D = 0.042 A_{C(K)} + 0.429 A_{C(U)} + 0.666 A_{C(Th)}$$

Where D is in nGy/hr and represents the absorbed dose rate in air due to the specific concentrations of; $A_{C(K)}$, $A_{C(U)}$ and $A_{C(Th)}$ in **Bq/Kg** respectively.

The absorbed dose rate itself does not give an indication of possible biological effects until it is converted to the dose equivalent, which is measured in sieverts S_v . The absorbed dose rate is Multiplied by a radiation weighing factor, is 1 for gamma radiation and 20 for alpha radiation because one G_y of alpha radiation is about 20 times more severe than one G_y of gamma radiation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The results of gamma ray spectrometric analysis are presented and interpreted for clarity and ease of comparison in Table 1 and Figure 2. The results of gamma spectrometric showed that measurable traces of radioisotopes that belong to the ²³⁸U, ⁴⁰K, and ²³²Th are present in the bituminous sands. This confirms the presence of these elements and their values agree with average normal concentrations in most soils.

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Table 1 - Radioactivity Concentrations Of ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , Radium Equivalent, Absorbed Dose Rate and Effective Dose of the samples collected

S/N	Sample Code	C_K (Bq/Kg)	C_R (Bq/Kg)	C_{Th} (Bq/Kg)	R_{eq} (Bq/Kg)	Absorbed Dose Rate (nGyh ⁻¹)	Effective Dose $\times 10^{-3}$ (mSvy ⁻¹)
1	ML 1	61.10±1.70	21.67±1.18	5.14±0.28	33.75±1.71	15.30±0.76	18.76±0.93
2	ML 2	109.12±2.27	22.50±1.20	2.06±0.17	33.85±1.62	15.66±0.72	19.21±0.88
3	ML 3	41.49±1.40	BDL	1.36±0.14	5.14±0.31	2.68±0.15	3.29±0.18
4	ML 4	BDL	1.16±0.27	BDL	1.16±0.27	0.495±0.12	0.61±0.15
5	ML 5	33.75±1.26	17.88±1.07	0.044±0.03	20.54±1.20	9.12±0.53	11.18±0.65
6	IGB 1	14.82±0.84	8.74±0.75	BDL	9.88±0.81	4.37±0.36	5.36±0.42
7	IGB 2	20.58±0.99	29.13±1.37	2.77±0.2	34.68±1.73	15.16±0.76	18.59±0.93
8	IGB 3	35.68±1.30	7.72±0.70	5.24±0.28	17.96±1.20	8.30±0.54	10.18±0.66
9	IGB 4	34.41±1.27	29.58±1.38	10.79±0.40	47.66±2.05	21.25±0.91	26.06±1.12
10	IGB 5	55.98±1.63	23.66±1.23	11.23±0.41	44.03±1.94	19.94±0.87	24.45±1.07
11	AGB 1	161.57±2.76	21.35±1.17	7.10±0.32	43.94±1.84	20.76±0.83	25.46±1.02
12	AGB 2	189.89±2.99	8.55±0.74	9.53±0.38	36.80±1.51	18.12±0.70	22.22±0.86
13	AGB 3	83.02±1.98	29.77±1.38	4.44±0.26	42.51±1.90	19.22±0.85	23.57±1.04
14	AGB 4	72.03±1.84	23.66±1.23	7.21±0.33	39.52±1.84	17.97±0.82	22.04±1.01
15	AGB 5	22.28±1.03	17.30±1.05	5.68±0.29	27.14±1.54	12.11±0.68	14.85±0.83
16	ILU 1	34.41±1.27	7.91±0.71	0.755±0.11	11.64±0.96	5.36±0.43	6.57±0.53
17	ILU 2	6.99±0.57	30.41±1.40	2.47±0.19	34.48±0.46	14.92±0.75	18.30±0.92
18	ILU 3	21.61±1.03	21.48±1.18	0.296±0.066	23.64±1.35	19.09±0.99	23.41±1.21
19	ILU 4	13.78±0.81	4.89±0.56	BDL	5.95±0.62	8.01±0.59	9.82±0.72
20	ILU 5	17.32±0.90	17.30±1.05	1.32±0.14	20.52±1.32	15.71±0.93	19.27±1.14
21	OKT 1	43.75±1.44	18.20±1.08	5.37±0.28	29.25±1.59	13.21±0.71	16.20±0.87
22	OKT 2	10.86±0.72	12.86±0.91	3.24±0.22	18.33±1.23	8.10±0.57	9.93±0.70
23	OKT 3	170.58±2.84	6.24±0.63	7.34±0.33	29.87±1.32	80.87±1.71	99.18±2.10
24	OKT 4	29.08±1.17	22.89±1.21	9.12±0.37	38.17±1.82	28.32±1.23	34.73±1.51
25	OKT 5	36.62±1.31	BDL	BDL	2.82±0.10	15.75±0.56	19.32±0.69
	AV±SD	52.83±0.72	16.19±0.41	4.10±0.14	26.13±0.57	16.39±0.32	20.10±0.40

Figure 2: Radioactivity Concentration of ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra and ^{232}Th in the Five Locations

According to UNSCEAR (2000), the world average of radioactive concentration of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K was given as 36, 37 and 420 Bq/kg respectively. And from the result obtained, the range of average radioactive concentration was 12.04 ± 0.48 in Okitipupa to 20.13 ± 0.24 in Agbadu, 0.968 ± 0.07 in Ilubirin to 6.79 ± 0.05 in Agbadu and 18.82 ± 0.26 in Ilubirin to 105.76 ± 0.78 in Agbadu all in Bq/Kg for of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K respectively. This shows that the values of these concentrations are highest in Agbadu.

On the environmental impact of the occurrence of radioelement in the study area, according to UNSCEAR (2000) the world average value outdoor exposure is $70 \mu\text{Sv}$, and the mean effective dose value obtained was $20.10 \mu\text{Sv}$ which is lower than world average value of outdoor exposure of $70 \mu\text{Sv}$. This is still below harmful Dose to human exposure. Therefore the result obtained showed that the presence of the bituminous cannot cause any health hazard now but a baseline study of this nature, coupled with data from other sampling media like well water, stream water and vegetation could help the government on regulatory policies on safety and monitoring, when full exploitation of the bituminous sands begins.

CONCLUSION

This work is aimed at detecting the presence and level of radioactivity concentration of radionuclides in the bituminous sand deposits of southwestern Nigeria. The results of the study using an integrated approach of gamma spectrometric method of analysis indicated that the radionuclides identified and quantified belong to the naturally occurring decay series of uranium, thorium, and potassium. The tar sands can be safely said to be non-radioactive as the measured activity in them is quite low.

The specific activities of radionuclides in the bituminous sands are not expected to constitute any health hazards now, but the mode of exploitation and extraction could be an important consideration in the future.

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